

Quantum Circuit Simulations on Multi-Channel Sound Systems

Spencer Topel¹, Parker Kuklinski²

¹Physical Synthesis

19 Morris Ave, Studio 103 - 11205 - Brooklyn - New York - USA

first.spencer@physical-synthesis.com, second.parkerkuklinski@gmail.com

Abstract. *This paper describes a set of sonification studies simulating a quantum circuit conducted on a 145 multi-channel speaker array at Virginia Tech in 2022. Using the audio software SuperCollider we deployed the gate implementation of a tensor circuit and the quantum Fourier transform to generate parameters used for different types of signal modulation, which were output to discrete speaker channels, with each basis state assigned to only one speaker at time. Analysis of each study is provided, along with links to Ambisonic recordings of the studies.*

1 Introduction

The purpose of this paper is to present a novel approach to sound synthesis using quantum circuit simulation. Unlike quantum hardware currently in development to create the first usable quantum computers, the mathematics and algorithms that will enable the software for these devices is already well into development. This particular kind of work is referred to as “simulation” of a quantum computer, which is intended to run on a quantum computer, but can instead be computed on a classical computing platform such as a personal computer or a super-computing cluster.

Figure 1: The Virginia Tech Cube, with over 145 independently addressable loudspeakers mounted to all four walls and the ceiling.

Our primary motivation for this study is to utilize a multi-channel sound system to observe simulated outputs from a quantum system. Specifically we are interested in the concept of few classical inputs consisting of classical sine-wave oscillators generating many entangled quantum outputs.

2 Background

In the burgeoning field of quantum music applications for musical, a number of exploratory applications have focused on the semantic aspects of musical composition [1], which includes note selection [2], rhythm or beat generation [3], and musical structure [4], and different combinations therein [5].

Less common are sound synthesis applications performed directly on or from a superconducting device primarily due to cost and access to the experimental hardware with two notable instances including by the present authors during a residency at the Yale Quantum Institute in 2019 [6] that utilized superconducting systems as hardware synthesizers sampling qubits directly for control and sonification purposes in a live musical improvisation, and more recently with the *Q1 Synth*, a software interface that allows players to perform measurements on real or simulated qubits configured in a particular way to configure settings in a classical software based sound synthesizer [7].

In the absence of hardware, a handful of experiments have been performed in the sound synthesis domain on simulation of quantum circuits and processes. Such investigations include simulation of quantum harmonic oscillators and particles [8, 9], and relevant to this study the simulation of quantum dynamics by Kontogeorgakopoulos and Burgarth [10]. For this paper, the authors sonified quantum dynamics in a stereo channel arrangement, which is discussed in further detail in Section 5.

The present authors have also explored sonification of quantum carpets [11], creating multi-harmonic soundscapes [12][13]. Quantum carpet sonification is most relevant to our study since we were able to produce similar results to the observe effects created in stereo, but on a much larger scale since using a multi-channel sound system with discrete outputs means more fully representing quantum dynamics through variational quantum oscillators simulations.

2.1 Variational Quantum Oscillator

A variational quantum circuit [14] is a parameterized quantum circuit $U(\theta)$ which takes classical data θ as input and outputs a quantum state $U(\theta)|\psi\rangle$. In practice, one will typically construct a cost function based on θ such that the output of $U(\theta)|\psi\rangle$ is close to a desired state $|\phi\rangle$, i.e.:

$$f(\theta) = |\langle\phi|U(\theta)|\psi\rangle|^2$$

These variational quantum circuits are used in algorithmic methods such as state preparation [15], variational quan-

Figure 2: Tensor product variational quantum oscillator. Pure initial state is transformed into equal superposition through Hadamard gates, and complex probability amplitudes are oscillated through rotation gates.

tum eigensolver (VQE) [16], and quantum machine learning [17]. Properly structuring these circuits presents a challenge as the usually low-dimensional structure of the classical input space necessarily cannot explore the entire output Hilbert space to produce a global optima. In this way, one would like to construct a variational circuit ansatz that is expressible, easy to implement, and likely to cover the target state.

We take the variational quantum circuit as inspiration for our variational quantum oscillator (VQO). Rather optimizing some cost function $f(\theta)$ dependent on the quantum output of a variational circuit, we instead *drive* that circuit by oscillating the classical data θ . In this way, $f(\theta)$ itself becomes an oscillator in response to the behavior of θ . Furthermore, this formalism allows for multi-channel output as for an n -qubit circuit we can map 2^{n+1} real dimensions of Hilbert space to real audio output. For these experiments, we designed 6-qubit circuits $U(\theta)$ and mapped both real and complex amplitudes of the basis states of $U(\theta)|\psi\rangle$ to 128 of the 145 speakers in Virginia Tech’s speaker array.

3 Selected VQO Ansätze

We designed two parameterized circuits to demonstrate the variational quantum oscillator. The first was a simple tensor product of 6 phase gates in series as seen in Figure 2. In this case, the amplitude for the $|\psi\rangle = |\psi_1\psi_2\psi_3\psi_4\psi_5\psi_6\rangle$ basis state following the application of $U(\theta)|0\rangle$ becomes

$$\langle\psi|U(\theta)|0\rangle = \exp\left(-\frac{i}{2}\sum_{k=1}^6(-1)^{\psi_k}\theta_k\right)$$

In this way, if we drive the R_Z gates by letting $\sigma_k = f_k t$, then each $\langle\psi|U(\theta)|0\rangle$ becomes a complex oscillator. These complex amplitudes can then be mapped to a 128 element speaker array. Further, if the frequencies are dynamically controlled in real-time, one can sonically “explore” the tensor structure of the Hilbert space.

Figure 3: Main entangling building block of the QFT-based VQO

Figure 4: A 6-qubit variational quantum oscillator based on the quantum Fourier transform

For example if we interpret ψ as a binary representation of a decimal (assume complex/real components of the same amplitude are grouped together), adjusting f_1 higher shifts the frequencies of speakers 1-64 negatively while positively shifting frequencies of speakers 65-128. Adjusting f_2 higher shifts the frequencies of speakers 1-32 and 65-96 negatively while positively shifting frequencies of speakers 33-64 and 97-128.

The second parameterized circuit considered was a parameterization of the quantum Fourier transform (QFT). In a circuit implementation of QFT on n qubits, $n - 1$ unique rotation gates are used which are denoted by $R_n = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \\ & \omega_N \end{pmatrix}$ where ω_N is the $N = 2^n$ root of unity. Rather than using these rotation gates with precise angles to recover the QFT, we instead treat the circuit as an VQC ansatz with $n - 1$ variable rotation gates, which we drive with different frequencies (see figures 2-3). Unlike in the previous tensor example, this ansatz explores entangled states within the Hilbert space.

4 The Quantum Cube Synthesizer

As part of the Virginia Tech I4 Artist Residency of 2022, we utilized The Cube at the Virginia Tech Moss Arts Center as a gigantic additive synthesizer by driving each individual speaker with a single oscillator to produce The Quantum Cube, which contrasts spherical representations of the qubit due to the acoustical layout of the loudspeakers. In this configuration, each audience performs a metaphorical *measurement* of the entire system by simply *listening*.

The use of constructive-destructive interference of acoustical waves from each speaker created a unique experience for each individual listener. Since The Cube contains over 145 addressable loudspeakers, we were able

to generate a wide range of signal interactions across the five-story high black box theater as shown in Figure 1.

4.1 The Tensor Circuit Ansätze SuperCollider Implementation

To realise this study, we utilized the widely available SuperCollider real-time audio programming platform to create our numerical simulations and sound processing algorithms. The basic structure our system was to first perform the numerical simulation to generate parameters for the classical digital synthesizer, similar to [10].

We started with the numerical simulation computations of the 6-qubit variational quantum oscillator presented in Section 2.1, shown in the block diagram-5. First we define a random unit vector computed once so that it does not update with random parameters, and instead use the random unit vector as a constant throughout the simulation. We then are then parameterized for our control. Multiplying these tensor rotation gates together provided a full unitary representation.

In parallel we created a Hadamard tensor matrix, representing a Hadamard operator to each individual qubit, as shown in the right column of Figure 5. From there we multiplied the Hadamard tensor with the rotation tensor, and then multiplied that product by the unit vector to produce a parameterized quantum circuit consisting of a rotation tensor composed with a Hadamard gate to mix the quantum states. Lastly, we used classical sound synthesis processing to produce the audible sonification.

Figure 5: Software Block diagram of The Quantum Cube Synthesizer simulation.

We composed a SuperCollider function to perform the additive sounds synthesis process played on The Quantum Cube multi-channel sound system. this synthesis amplitude modulation algorithm used generated sine waves with frequencies derived from the real values of the complex amplitude basis states from the numerical simulation described in Section 2.1. Figure 6 illustrates the processing performed in the algorithm, starting with the configuration of the modulation oscillator, followed by the initialization of a fixed-value carrier signal.

Amplitude modulation was performed between

the carrier signal and a modulation basis function, the combination of which was attenuated using a monotonic decreasing function to control the decay (loudness) of the tone over some user specified duration.

In addition to the quantum modulation synthesis shown in Figure 6, we derived three additional permutations of this audio processing approach consisting of:

- **Additive Synthesis** Fixed attenuation of a single frequency copied across 64 channels of loudspeakers without modulation.
- **Phase Modulation I** Phase modulation variant using the phase modulation function included in the SuperCollider library.
- **Phase Modulation II** Phase modulation variant using a phase modulation function created by the authors.

which we turn produced sonifications examples using identical input parameters.

5 Results and Conclusions

Running these simulations on a multi-channel audio system offered several extensions of previous work on quantum system dynamics [10]. Namely, the authors characterized three quantum dynamics, two of which that were of particular interest to our study:

- **Correlations:** resulting from particle interactions or entanglement between two or more particles.
- **Interferences:** wave dynamics dominated by interference.

In addition to providing descriptions of these dynamics, they provided their own observations to the sonification. Namely, that the correlation effects were distinctly audible as “movement and echoes between the stereo channels”, and that the interferences generated distinctively audible constructive (loud transient peaks), and destructive (silence) interactions, between the different synthesized tones [10].

Since the observed dynamics involved only two audio channels played back over stereo speakers, it was our aim to see if the observations could be expanded to a much larger array of speakers. As mentioned in Section 4, early testing showed that we needed to apply a decay function to the synthesized tones, similar to the physical modelling approached used by Jean-Claude Risset and David Wessel in construction of the acoustic bell model as a computer synthesis representation of physical modelling synthesis [18].

To do this we applied a simple decreasing monotononic scaling function to the amplitude of each basis-function modulated carrier signal, specified by some duration in seconds. In future work we plan to apply other dynamics, such as the imaginary part of the complex signal, to this attenuation function, which should in turn reveal new kinds of signal interactions.

To our surprise, the increase in individual outputs to each loudspeaker greatly enhanced the correlations and

CLASSICAL SOUND SYNTHESIS PROCESSING

```
//create oscillators with basis states frequencies
modulationBasisStates = {SinOsc.ar(basisStates.mod(2pi)*scalar)};

//initialize a fixed value carrier signal
carrierSignal = [SinOsc.ar(carrierSignalFrequency, phase, amplitude)];

//perform signal modulation and output to DAC
Out.ar(out,((carrierSignal * modulationBasisStates)) * Line.kr(1, 0, seconds));
```

Figure 6: A SuperCollider code snippet demonstrating a basic amplitude modulation of the quantum basis functions with a fixed carrier signal.

interferences [10] observed by the authors and residency participants. Notably, using the amplitude modulation algorithm presented in Figure 6 produced depth of echoes and spatialization that was both satisfyingly rich and very clear, almost like hearing music played in a reverberant acoustic space such as a cathedral or large concert hall. At the end of the residency, we recorded a live coding composition on the Quantum Cube entitled "Alice Apple", using a Zoom *H3 – VR* Ambisonic recording device [19].

6 Future Work

The framework described in this paper is useful for understanding the structure of these operators such as QFT or other notable quantum circuits. In the future, we see experimentation with more complex quantum circuits since they should produce more musically interesting interactions. Higher number of qubits would also be meaningful for this kind of simulation since the interactions will begin to express richer features such longer time scales or higher-order harmonic effects.

We also see the possibility for interactive musical interfaces for these algorithms that allow performers to use the synthesis in a live electronic spatialization or improvisation context. This is a logical progression towards making a usable synthesizer application with actual quantum computers in the future. However, it is worth noting that with current limitations of quantum hardware, we do not have access to quantum probability amplitudes as a classical observer. If and when hardware can overcome this limitation, the amplitudes could be sampled using a conventional signal processing framework.

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